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ON NEW MODIFICATIONS OF CMC-TEXTS CONTENT-ANALYSIS

Abstract. The thesis analyzes the distinctive features of new modifications of content analysis – action analysis (analysis aimed at identifying actions-in-text in computer-mediated communication (CMC)) and interaction analysis (analysis of interactions between CMC actors), the purpose of which is to identify and count different actions and interactions in CMC texts. It is noted that both action analysis and interaction analysis have as their subject «procedural», dynamically developing texts. The study of CMC requires the sociologist to do «double» work – analysis of the messages of CMC actors recorded on electronic media, as well as preliminary participation in the process of communication online in order to achieve an understanding of the context and direction of CMC.

Keywords: action analysis, interaction analysis, content analysis, CMC.

Анотація. У тезах проаналізовано відмінні риси, переваги та недоліки двох нових модифікацій контент-аналізу — action-analysis (аналіз, націлений на виявлення actions-in-text, що практикуються в кіберпросторі) та interaction-analysis (аналіз ситуацій взаємодії кіберакторів), мета яких – виявлення та підрахунок різних акцій та інтеракцій в онлайн текстах. Відзначено, що action-analysis та interaction-analysis мають своїм предметом «процесуальні» тексти, що динамічно розвиваються. Вивчення кіберкомунікування вимагає від соціолога «подвійної» роботи – аналізу записаних на електронні носії повідомлень кіберакторів, а також попередньої участі у процесі «плетіння розмовних ниток» online, щоб досягти розуміння контексту та спрямованості кіберкомунікації.

Ключові слова: action analysis, interaction analysis, контент-аналіз, комп'ютеро-опосередкована комунікація (CMC).

Computer-mediated communication (CMC) has specific features that must be taken into account when choosing a method for sociological research of this phenomenon: messages are presented mainly in text form («emoticons» can also be considered as a kind of text); messages are predominantly actional in nature, being symbols of certain actions of cyber actors (actional messages make up almost 90% of the total volume of chat messages, while 10% are informational messages [1]). Since CMC is presented in text form and has an actional nature, for its analysis it is necessary to choose methods that have as their goal (1) the analysis of textual phenomena, and (2) the analysis of social actions [2].

According to P. Trudgill, the disciplines that study the texts from a social perspective can be divided into three groups: 1) those whose goals are purely sociological; these disciplines are aimed at revealing the hidden social organization of the text (ethnomethodology); 2) disciplines that deal partly with linguistic, partly with social factors (conversation analysis, sociolinguistics); 3) disciplines whose goals are purely linguistic (linguistics, pragmatics) [3, p. 7]. It is obvious that the most sociological of the three varieties of methodology is ethnomethodology, which involves

conducting participant observation, in-depth interviewing, and «breaching experiments». It is advisable to supplement the use of these ethnographic techniques with content analysis aimed at identifying certain categorical units in studied texts. If traditional content analysis aims to measure the frequency of occurrence in the text of certain «words, topics, characters, paragraphs, points, concepts, semantics» [4, p. 246–247] (that is, linguistic units of analysis), then content analysis, which has action-in-text as its subject is aimed at measuring the frequency of occurrence in CMC-texts the actions and interactions belonging to certain semantic categories. So, the study of CMC requires the development of two new modifications of content analysis – action-analysis (analysis aimed at identifying actions-in-text) and interaction-analysis (analysis of interactions between CMC actors), the purpose of which is to identify and count various actions and interactions in CMC texts.

According to W. Neuman, content analysis is a technique for analyzing the content of a text. «Content» refers to words, meanings, pictures, symbols, ideas, themes, or any other message that may be conveyed. «Text» is something written, visually depicted, or spoken, which serves as an intermediary in communication [5, p. 272–273]. Whatever the object of traditional content analysis (word, meaning, picture, symbol, idea, theme, or any other message of communication), it is in any case aimed at fixing «static» categorical units, while action-analysis and interaction-analysis have as their subject «procedural», dynamically developing texts. Let us single out one more procedural aspect of action-analysis and interaction-analysis of CMC. CMC-texts that are written in an open network (unlike those already published, which have a complete character), have open and incomplete graphics and semantics. Therefore, the study of actional and interactional messages, in this case, presupposes the presence of a researcher within the CMC community, and his/her participation in the process of CMC. Analyzing fragments of CMC recorded on electronic media, the researcher runs the risk of not understanding the essence of what is happening, and not capturing the background features of messages presented in CMC texts. Thus, the study of CMC requires the sociologist to do «double» work: the analysis of CMC actors' messages recorded on electronic media, and preliminary participation in the process of «weaving conversational threads» online in order to achieve an understanding of the context and direction of CMC.

The content analysis contains the characteristics of both quantitative and qualitative research [1]. Action analysis and interaction analysis, as modifications of content analysis, also include characteristics of both qualitative and quantitative research. Their goal is to identify the frequency of actions and interactions in CMC texts, which is associated with quantitative analysis. On the other hand, since specific actions and interactions may have unique and inimitable content, qualitative analysis is needed to assign them to a certain category. If the traditional content analysis is facilitated by the presence of a given set of words or phrases that must be found in the text and requires a procedure that can be performed automatically using special computer programs, the action analysis and interaction analysis require a completely

different approach. These methods deal with certain types of actions and interactions that can be filled with different content in different conversational contexts, so it is impossible to develop an encoding at the level of individual words and phrases in this case. Computer implementation of action analysis and interaction analysis can give rise to erroneous interpretations of the text; one should prefer the live professional work of a person.

What are the advantages of action analysis and interaction analysis? 1) These methods are combined with the participant observation method, since actions and interactions can be understood if you are «inside» CMC, synchronously tracking conversational dynamics (observing the text behavior of CMC actors). Thus, the action analysis and interaction analysis methods «push» the boundaries of the content analysis method and suggest its combination with the participant observation method. 2) In contrast to the online questionnaire, which involves the «discovery» of the researcher (which can have the effect of a certain insincerity of CMC actors, as well as blocking their spontaneous discourse reactions), the use of the action analysis and interaction analysis does not require the deanonymization of the researcher, as a result, the natural flow of CMC is not disturbed. How ethical is the implementation of the «guerrilla» research project (a metaphor proposed by G. Yang [6, p. 471]) is a question of interest to very many Western sociologists. According to J. Androutsopoulos [7], the problem can be mitigated by the fact that CMC is «public» (and not private): since CMC actors have made a free decision to expose their social text-practices to the public, the researcher acquires the right to study and interpret virtual interaction. 3) Since action analysis and interaction analysis are of a «procedural» nature, they can be used to explore dynamic changes in the social space of CMC communication. 4) The following advantage of action analysis and interaction analysis is common to all modifications of content analysis. We are talking about the low cost of this method, which can be effectively applied by two researchers (rather than a whole research group), the use of which can be regularly renewed almost every month (whereas the survey is carried out at large time intervals) [4, p. 258].

Among the shortcomings of content analysis, B. Berg mentions its limitation to the study of only documents recorded [4, p. 259]. However, in the case of studying CMC messages, this can hardly be considered a disadvantage, since the electronic recording of CMC does not cause any difficulties. Another disadvantage of content analysis, according to B. Berg, is its inefficiency in testing causal relationships between categorical variations: if you measure the frequency of occurrence of certain categories of analysis in the text every two weeks, then it will be possible to establish their significance, but not the reason for their appearance [4, p. 259]. Thus, according to B. Berg, content analysis can be useful for studying processes in social groups that are recorded in the text; it can become indispensable in descriptive research; but at the same time, it is ineffective if the purpose of the study is to elucidate the causes of a certain social phenomenon.

One can conclude that, as for action analysis and interaction analysis, when they are used simultaneously, the indicated shortcoming of content analysis can be partly neutralized,

since the reasons for the popularity of certain interactions can be found in the actional dimension of CMC. Since interactions consist of chains of actions, the frequency of occurrence of certain interactions in CMC may be due to the high demand for actions belonging to a certain categorical type [8]. For example, the high frequency of conflict interactions in CMC depends to a certain extent on the frequency of brutal action messages used by CMC actors.

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